

Original Research

The Role of Ambidextrous Leadership in Employee Performance: A Literature Review on Manufacturing Industry

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Abstract

Employee performance becomes a strategic issue for companies facing the VUCA era (Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, and Ambiguity) following the subsiding of the Covid-19 pandemic. During the Covid-19 pandemic, social distancing strategies were implemented, necessitating the discontinuation of gatherings in public areas. This led companies to change their work arrangements, such as adopting work-from-home practices. From the previous norm of employees working collectively and centrally in offices and business locations, there was a drastic shift to employees being dispersed and working from their respective homes. This research aims to investigate the implications of ambidextrous leadership on employee performance on manufacturing industry. The research process employed a literature review approach, conducted comprehensively. The research results suggest that ambidextrous leadership affects employee performance. This study demonstrates that the type of ambidextrous leadership can enhance the likelihood of achieving business targets on manufacturing industry. This presents a challenge for future business development because the performance of employees working in the manufacturing industry sector greatly depends on a leadership style that can stimulate them through the innovation process.

Keywords: Ambidextrous Leadership, Employee Performance, Manufacturing Industry.

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Introduction

A drastic transformation has occurred globally in human life due to the Covid-19 pandemic, resulting in over 275 million confirmed cases and 5.36 million fatalities across more than 103 countries as of December 2021 (Saputra et al., 2022). The pandemic has given rise to social, economic, environmental, and even energy crises. Furthermore, the Covid-19 pandemic has introduced social distancing strategies, necessitating the cessation of communal activities in public spaces, including within companies, which have had to adapt their work arrangements. Prior to the Covid-19 pandemic, all employees worked in physical office spaces or company business locations. However, during the pandemic, there was a drastic shift towards remote and dispersed work arrangements, with employees working from their respective homes (Saputra et al., 2022). Working remotely became a prevalent work arrangement during the Covid-19 era, although its implementation raised questions due to reduced collaboration and work efficiency. While working remotely, whether from home or other locations outside the office, employees may experience professional or social isolation resulting from limited formal face-to-face communication in the workplace (Merkuž & Mihelič, 2023).

Covid-19 serves as a tangible example illustrating the emergence of the VUCA (Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, and Ambiguity) era. The concept of VUCA represents a business environment characterized by volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity. It has brought about fundamental changes leading people and managing organizations (Saputra, 2022). The Covid-19 pandemic has led to the depletion of personal resources, including physical and mental burdens experienced by employees, which are essential elements of the job resources required for employees to engage effectively in their work. Employees with good work engagement tend to remain productive and maintain their performance even in the face of difficulties or challenging times. Work engagement serves as a protective factor for employees in coping with the uncertainty and limitations posed by the Covid-19 pandemic (Saputra et al., 2022).

Even as the Covid-19 pandemic subsides, companies continue to face disruptive turbulence in the VUCA era, demanding greater agility and resilience. Business agility, when viewed as organizational agility, encompasses specific dimensions supported by agility enablers and triggered by agility drivers (Saputra, 2022). Thriving in today's challenging environment also requires companies to be innovative, as innovation promises competitive advantages. Innovation in work involves generating, promoting, and realizing ideas to enhance product quality, process effectiveness, and company work methods (Irum Jabeen et al., 2023). Organizations in contemporary companies are distinguished by the complexity of their leaders due to the high pressure to innovate in the market (Alemu et al., 2023).

In recent years, there has been an increased focus on enhancing leaders' abilities to think and act innovatively, also known as their creative performance. Ambidextrous leadership is a relatively new leadership style that facilitates leaders' capacity to think and act innovatively or exhibit creative performance (Mutonyi & Lien, 2023). This relatively new leadership style is suggested to promote innovation at the individual, team, and organizational levels (Akıncı et al., 2022). Ambidextrous leadership has become a recent

research focus that facilitates innovation by generating ideas and taking risks within organizations, thus making them more efficient and enhancing existing knowledge and skills within the company (Irum Jabeen et al., 2023). Ambidextrous leadership is a leadership style where leaders encourage employees through innovation processes, respond intelligently, and smoothly facilitate the implementation of innovation (Ahmad et al., 2022).

Ambidextrous leadership behaviors enhance team performance, particularly in environments characterized by high uncertainty and autonomy. This leadership style can stimulate collaboration among employees through an inspiring shared vision and high-performance expectations (Alo, 2023). Ambidextrous leadership, defined as the interaction of two complementary leadership behaviors, namely exploration and exploitation, encourages employees to proactively seek new ideas and solutions (Andrini & Susanto, 2022). It is crucial to examine and improve employee performance using the goal-setting theory, which asserts that a company's success in achieving its objectives is measured by employee performance and outcomes. Previous research has found that job satisfaction, work motivation, leadership style, and competencies all influence performance declines in cases where employees fail to reach their goals (Hajjali et al., 2022).

Leaders are individuals who can motivate, guide, or influence a large group of people to follow their directives and aspire to achieve common goals. Leadership is a designation based on qualifications, agreed upon by signs of eligibility for membership in the leadership that leads an organization (Hajjali et al., 2022). There are two components in management by exception related to employee performance. The first is passive, where leaders influence behavior and use corrective measures or punishments in response to poor performance or deviations from standards. The second is active, where leaders actively monitor employees' work and use corrective actions to ensure that tasks are carried out and completed according to standards (Hajjali et al., 2022). Leadership strategies are related to the environment, and innovation differentiation strategies are associated with internal and external adjustments and structures, which significantly influence performance (Yusuf Iis et al., 2022).

One of the growing sectors in Indonesia is the manufacturing industry, but it faces challenges in competing competitively (Agung Wahyu Handaru et al., 2021). The role of the manufacturing industry in the Indonesian economy has weakened over the past decade. Between 1980 and 2000, the contribution of the manufacturing industry to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) increased from 15.26 percent to 26.38 percent. However, in 2019, the contribution of the manufacturing industry decreased to only 21.68 percent, representing a decrease of 4.7 percent in less than 10 years (Rahmi et al., 2022). This decline is attributed to the reduced contribution of the manufacturing industry to the national GDP and a shift towards the tertiary or service sector (Sari & Oktor, 2021). The Covid-19 pandemic also resulted in a decline in stock prices for manufacturing companies, both before and after the announcement of the pandemic in Indonesia. On average, stock prices of manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange experienced a sharp decline after the announcement of the Covid-19 pandemic in Indonesia (Malfrita & Sari, 2022).

Every manufacturing company requires a track that aligns with its core business, enabling it to measure its growth and development accurately (Tiara et al., 2021). For the manufacturing industry to regain strength and support Indonesia's economic growth, the performance of the manufacturing sector must be enhanced through improved competitiveness. Enhancing competitiveness can be achieved by increasing employee productivity (Rahmi et al., 2022). Issues related to unsuccessful leadership styles within a company are one of the causes of low job satisfaction, poor performance, and decreased employee productivity. Leaders who fail to demonstrate effective leadership within an organization can be identified when their subordinates struggle to accept their leadership, are not easily directed, engage in maneuvering, and fail to be influenced to achieve the company's productivity targets (Hajiali et al., 2022). Leader behavior has an impact on the performance of subordinates. Subordinates with servant leaders tend to have high levels of engagement and loyalty, which have the potential to contribute to higher productivity levels (Purwanto et al., 2021).

Employee performance refers to how an individual efficiently and effectively utilizes techniques and time to achieve the goals set by the company. In addition to employee performance, the manufacturing industry sector can continue to thrive due to other support factors within the company, such as ambidextrous leadership. This leadership style involves leaders encouraging employees through the innovation process, responding intelligently, and smoothly facilitating the implementation of innovation, thereby enabling the company to achieve its productivity targets (Ahmad et al., 2022). This study conceptually elucidates the implications of ambidextrous leadership on employee performance. Ambidextrous leadership style important in the manufacturing industry sector. This presents a challenge for future business development because the performance of employees working in the manufacturing industry sector greatly depends on a leadership style that can stimulate them through the innovation process.

This article discusses the implications presented by ambidextrous leadership as part of improving employee performance. The problem discussed in this article includes the role of ambidextrous leadership in manufacturing companies. The components of measuring ambidextrous leadership must be explained in detail to play a role in improving employee performance. The preparation of this research will provide added value for those discussing ambidextrous leadership. Employee performance as a result of planned and systematic measurements requires the role of ambidextrous leadership. This literature review specifically discusses the position of ambidextrous leadership as part of improving employee performance. Business sustainability is determined by the quality of performance and the ability of employees to achieve the best performance.

Theoretical Review

Ambidextrous Leadership

Ambidexterity has garnered significant attention in the past two decades (Tushman & O'Reilly, 1996, as cited in Irum Jabeen et al., 2023). It has been studied at both individual and team levels, where ambidexterity refers to the efficient use of both hands simultaneously (Van Den Bosch & Volberda, 2007, as cited in Irum Jabeen et al., 2023). Ambidextrous leadership, as an approach in leadership, is viewed as the ability to foster

the emergence of explorative and exploitative behaviors in individuals who are team members (Saputra, 2022). Ambidextrous leadership is delineated into two primary behaviors: opening behavior, which encourages innovation, allowing tasks to be performed differently through experimentation, and closing behavior, which promotes efficiency by ensuring goal compliance, supervision, corrective actions, and the establishment of specific guidelines (Saputra, 2022). Ambidextrous leadership, defined as the interaction of two complementary leadership behaviors, namely exploration and exploitation, encourages employees to proactively seek new ideas and solutions (Andrini & Susanto, 2022).

Ambidextrous leadership is also associated with job enrichment, especially in repetitive jobs, as the combination of explorative and exploitative tasks not only increases interest levels but also the meaningfulness of work (Alo, 2023). By combining these two distinct yet complementary leadership behaviors, namely opening and closing behaviors, leaders can effectively stimulate explorative and exploitative efforts among their followers (Akıncı et al., 2022). First, open leadership behavior supports followers in breaking routines, challenging the status quo, and generating new ideas in the workplace. Open leadership behavior enhances follower variability, such as encouraging innovation and efforts to change existing approaches or create resources for independent thinking (Ahmad et al., 2022). Second, closed leadership behavior encompasses taking corrective actions, establishing routines, imposing sanctions for errors, and so forth. Closed leadership behavior seeks to reduce follower variability by controlling goal progress, taking disciplinary measures, or establishing strict guidelines (Ahmad et al., 2022).

Ambidextrous leadership style has been proposed as a promising leadership approach aimed at facilitating the professional ability to think creatively and act innovatively (Mutonyi & Lien, 2023). The rationale behind this is that the complexity of innovation activities needs to be balanced with an equally complex leadership approach. Therefore, ambidextrous leadership is recommended as a beneficial approach to accommodate and address the complexities inherent in innovation activities by combining the capacity to lead from the front and from behind. Ambidextrous leaders act as catalysts for innovative work behaviors among employees, where they encourage employees to demonstrate innovative behaviors for workplace success by engaging in both exploration and exploitation behaviors (Irum Jabeen et al., 2023). Leaders with ambidextrous leadership behaviors are better equipped to engage in the process of assisting employees in overcoming and understanding new situations, as well as encouraging them to explore (Merkuž & Mihelič, 2023).

Specifically, employee ambidexterity mediates the positive relationship between high-performance work systems and employee job performance, but the extent of the mediating effect depends on the level of ambidextrous leadership (Alemu et al., 2023). The alignment between employee goals and company goals is influenced, in part, by leadership styles, both positively and negatively (Fatyandri et al., 2023). In general, when employees perceive a higher level of ambidextrous leadership, the positive relationship between high-performance work systems and employee ambidexterity becomes stronger. Consequently, employee ambidexterity will transmit the influence of high-performance work systems to employee job performance. Conversely, when employees perceive a lower level of ambidextrous leadership, the positive relationship between high-

performance work systems and employee job performance weakens. Therefore, leaders need to be trained in ambidextrous leadership to enhance employee innovative performance (Irum Jabeen et al., 2023).

Employee Performance

Employee performance refers to the quality and quantity of work achieved by an employee in carrying out their responsibilities (Chevy Herli Sumerli et al., 2022). Enhancing employee performance is crucial and desired both by employees and companies. Companies seek optimal employee performance for improved work outcomes and profitability. On the other hand, employees have an interest in personal development and job promotion. To meet both these desires, a robust performance management system is essential. The benchmark for assessing good employee performance is the ability of employees to carry out job tasks in accordance with the standards set by the company. When employees are unable to fulfill their duties or obligations as required by the company's leadership, their performance can be considered poor (Rivaldo & Nabella, 2023).

Numerous empirical studies have examined the relationship between human resource practices and employee performance in various fields (Mira et al., 2019). Performance is the outcome or level of success of an individual over a specific period in carrying out tasks compared to various factors such as work standards, targets or goals, and predefined and mutually agreed criteria (Andreas, 2022). The tasks or jobs performed here consistently maintain high standards, including four performance evaluation criteria: accuracy, precision, skill, and cleanliness (Ain Abdullah & Hossain, 2021). Performance can be viewed in terms of speed, quality, service, and value, meaning the speed of work processes with reliable quality, good service, and value seen in employee performance achievement, which can affect company performance (Yusuf Iis et al., 2022).

Employee performance can influence the functioning of an organizational company. The better the performance displayed by employees, the more it helps in the development of the organization or company (Sugiarti, 2021). Employee performance is not just information for promotions or salary determinations for the company but also about how the company can develop employee careers and plan to improve performance declines. To enhance employee performance, companies must be able to improve the quality of employees by providing good training standards and a conducive working environment (Agus Salim et al., 2022). Companies should focus on maintaining employee satisfaction and happiness to boost productivity. Existing literature also emphasizes that satisfied employees enhance performance and contribute significantly to overall company achievements (Al-Ali et al., 2019). The success of a company is closely linked to the job satisfaction of its employees (Novitasari et al., 2021).

The design of work systems in manufacturing industries significantly supports the creation of productive, comfortable, and efficient work, thus having a significant impact on improving work quality in the industrial world (Sukhron Makhmudah et al., 2022). Many companies derive benefits from training programs, performance evaluations, and work systems based on corporate regulations, where these guidelines are intended to develop a loyal workforce because it leads to longer-term employment (Ilmiah et al.,

2021). The ability to empower employees within a company effectively, placing employees in positions that match their abilities and interests without neglecting the ethical values of psychological needs and expectations, allows employees to feel comfortable and happy in their jobs over time. Employee loyalty and job satisfaction have been prioritized as critical issues, and companies aim to utilize and manage human resources effectively (Ilmiah et al., 2021).

Research Method

This research utilized a literature review approach. Books, journals, research reports, and secondary data were used support the research findings. The research process began by recognizing the significance of ambidextrous leadership in enhancing employee performance. Ambidexterity has been a widely researched topic in leadership styles within organizations or companies. Companies needed to raise awareness of the urgency of ambidextrous leadership among all employees, as leadership is a crucial component for improving employee performance and achieving the company's productivity targets.

The literature review method involved the use of theories, concepts, and relevant findings to address the research problem (Azmy & Malanov, 2021). The analysis was presented in a narrative manner and compared with journals as the primary source. The urgency of this topic was established based on the manufacturing industry's strong need for employee performance influenced by the role of ambidextrous leadership. The ability of ambidextrous leaders to stimulate explorative and exploitative behaviors was essential to facilitate employees' creative thinking and innovative actions.

Result and Discussion

The literature review method was employed in this research to uncover the implications of ambidextrous leadership on employee performance. The conceptual framework of the study is depicted in the following model:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Based on the theoretical review and the conceptual framework above, several supporting indicators are required to assess employee performance. According to Koopmans et al. (2013) as cited in Alemu et al. (2023), there are four broad and generic dimensions of employee performance: Task performance, which refers to an employee's proficiency in performing core job tasks. Contextual performance, which pertains to employee behaviors that support the organizational, social, and psychological environment in which primary job tasks are conducted. Adaptive performance, which relates to an employee's ability to adapt to changes in roles or the work environment. Counterproductive work behavior, which refers to behaviors that harm the well-being of

the organization or company. A positive relationship exists between employee performance and employee ambidexterity in companies (Kobarg et al., 2015 as cited in Alemu et al., 2023). Individual or employee ambidexterity is a cognitive ability required to balance exploration and exploitation efforts (Good & Michel, 2013 as cited in Alemu et al., 2023).

To evaluate employee performance, it is crucial to consider not only the four dimensions mentioned above but also internal and external factors. Internal factors originate from within the employees themselves, while external factors are the supportive elements from the work environment (Chevy Herli Sumerli et al., 2022). According to Gomes (2003) as cited in Yusuf Iis et al. (2022) there are eight indicators of employee performance: Quantity of work (i.e., the volume of tasks completed within a specific time frame), Quality of work (i.e., the quality of work results in terms of compliance and readiness, Creativity (i.e., the originality of ideas presented by employees and their actions in problem-solving), Collaboration (i.e., The willingness of employees to cooperate with their colleagues), Reliability (i.e., Employee consciousness and trustworthiness regarding attendance and task completion), Initiative (i.e., the enthusiasm to take on new tasks and increase responsibilities), Job knowledge (i.e., The breadth of knowledge about the job and relevant skills), and personal qualities, which include personality, leadership, friendliness, and personal integrity.

To enhance employee performance, it is not limited to dimensions, factors, or indicators alone. Leadership style also plays a crucial role in improving employee performance within a company. Ambidextrous leadership is considered a promising leadership style aimed at facilitating employees' ability to think creatively and act innovatively (Mutonyi & Lien, 2023). Ambidextrous leadership is defined as the interaction between two complementary leadership behaviors, opening and closing, where explorative and exploitative strengths drive employees proactively to seek new ideas and solutions (Andrini & Susanto, 2022). Exploration involves uncovering hidden potentials in each employee through in-depth examination and research, while exploitation is the utilization of employee performance empowerment based on the potentials discovered through the exploration process (Wibawa et al., 2024).

Ambidextrous leadership style facilitates employees' ability to think creatively and act innovatively because the complexity of innovation activities needs to be balanced with an equally complex leadership approach. Therefore, ambidextrous leadership is recommended as a beneficial approach to accommodate and address the complexity within innovation activities, combining the capacity to lead from the front and the rear (Mutonyi & Lien, 2023). In a company, leaders must be adept at problem-solving, as this is a crucial process in improving company performance. A leader, in solving problems, needs to understand the deficiencies within the company, analyze graphical diagrams, and provide the best solutions to the company. Problem-solving is closely related to creativity because effective problem-solving requires creative thinking and effective solutions (Wibawa et al., 2024).

Ambidexterity in employees mediates a positive relationship between high-performance work systems and employee job performance. However, the magnitude of the mediating effect depends on the level of ambidextrous leadership (Alemu et al., 2023).

When employees perceive a higher level of ambidextrous leadership, the positive relationship between high-performance work systems and employee ambidexterity becomes stronger. Consequently, employee ambidexterity will transmit the influence of high-performance work systems to employee job performance. Conversely, when employees perceive a lower level of ambidextrous leadership, the positive relationship between high-performance work systems and employee job performance weakens. Therefore, leaders need to be trained in ambidextrous leadership to enhance employee innovative performance (Irum Jabeen et al., 2023).

Several studies indicate that ambidextrous leadership affects employee performance, so companies should enhance ambidextrous leadership styles to improve work quality and productivity, ultimately supporting the achievement of company targets. The design of work systems in the manufacturing industry significantly contributes to creating productive, comfortable, and efficient work, thereby enhancing work quality in the industrial sector (Sukhron Makhmudah et al., 2022). The manufacturing industry can continue to thrive due to the support of ambidextrous leadership, where leaders encourage employees through innovation processes, respond intelligently, and smoothly facilitate the implementation of innovation, enabling the achievement of company productivity targets (Ahmad et al., 2022).

The Effect of Ambidextrous Leadership on Employee Performance

Ambidextrous leadership is the ability of leaders to exercise leadership amid dynamic changes by applying two contrasting approaches simultaneously: being oriented towards exploratory innovation and oriented towards efficient exploitation (Mueller et al., 2020, as cited in Saputra et al., 2022). One of the growing sectors in Indonesia is the manufacturing industry, but it still faces challenges in competing competitively (Agung Wahyu Handaru et al., 2021). To strengthen the manufacturing industry and support Indonesia's economic growth, the performance of the manufacturing industry must be improved through increased competitiveness, which can be achieved by enhancing employee productivity (Rahmi et al., 2022). Issues related to leadership styles that are not effectively applied within a company are one of the causes of low job satisfaction, poor performance, and decreased employee productivity (Hajiali et al., 2022). Therefore, ambidextrous leadership is one of the key components in employee performance. Some strategies of ambidextrous leadership that companies can implement include the following:

Figure 2. Implications of Ambidextrous Leadership

The manufacturing industry sector can continue to thrive due to the support of ambidextrous leadership, where leaders encourage employees through innovation processes, respond intelligently, and smoothly facilitate the implementation of innovation, enabling the achievement of company productivity targets (Ahmad et al., 2022). The depiction above illustrates that ambidextrous leadership, or ambidextrous leadership style, presents a unique challenge for companies. The implication is that the achievement of employee performance must be supported by both exploratory and exploitative behaviors. Exploratory behavior involves uncovering every hidden potential within each employee through in-depth examination and research, while exploitative behavior entails harnessing employee performance empowerment based on potential already identified through the exploration process (Wibawa et al., 2024). Training steps with managers and their teams, focusing on balancing exploration and exploitation in the work process, will clearly lead to sustained positive impacts, such as employee well-being. The positive influence of ambidextrous leadership on sustainable impacts like employee well-being indicates that managers, in addition to their competence in self-management and personnel management, also develop competence in actively shaping exploratory and exploitative elements within the organizational framework of the company (Rigotti, 2013, as cited in Kraft, 2018).

Exploratory leader behavior is interpreted as open leadership behavior, including allowing employees to complete tasks differently, encouraging experimentation, motivating risk-taking, enhancing the likelihood of independent thinking and action, creating space for individual ideas, allowing for mistakes to happen, and encouraging learning from them. In contrast, exploitative leader behavior is interpreted as closed leadership behavior, including assisting in setting routines, controlling goal achievement, taking corrective action, ensuring compliance with rules, focusing on uniform task completion, imposing sanctions for errors, and adhering firmly to plans (Merkuž & Mihelič, 2023). Ambidextrous leaders demonstrate temporal flexibility, which is the ability to switch between the two behaviors as needed by the situation (Rosing et al., 2011, as cited in Merkuž & Mihelič, 2023).

Ambidextrous leadership is also associated with job enrichment, especially in "repetitive" jobs, because the combination of exploratory and exploitative tasks not only enhances interest but also the meaningfulness of work (Parker, 2014, as cited in Alo, 2023). Therefore, ambidextrous leadership is necessary for resource allocation and managing the blend of exploratory and exploitative activities within a team (Rogan & Mors, 2014, as cited in Alo, 2023). From studies on exploitation and exploration, it has been proven that team leader exploration activities involve knowledge transfer from bottom to top, while their exploitation activities consist of knowledge transfer from top to bottom. Specifically, team leader exploration activities involve the search for new ideas, unique competencies, new businesses, new strategies, new target markets, and experimenting with new production techniques while reviewing existing beliefs and choices. On the other hand, exploitation involves refining and extending existing technology, applying existing competencies, enhancing and applying existing product and technical knowledge, all while expanding existing beliefs and choices (Mom et al., 2007, as cited in Alo, 2023).

Several literature reviews on the influence of ambidextrous leadership in companies have been presented by Roth & Bosener (2015, as cited in Kraft, 2018), which were summarized from the results of empirical studies by various earlier researchers. The hypothesis testing results from these studies reveal the positive influence of ambidextrous leadership in companies, including: ambidextrous leadership has a positive impact on revenue in the manufacturing sector (He, Z. L., & Wong, P. K., 2004, as cited in Kraft, 2018), a positive influence through ambidextrous leadership on performance for large companies (Lubatkin, M. et al. 2006, as cited in Kraft, 2018), a positive influence of ambidextrous leadership on the market share of start-up companies (Han, M. & Celly, N., 2008, as cited in Kraft, 2018), a positive influence of ambidextrous leadership on the profit and loss of R&D companies (Uotila, J. et al., 2009, as cited in Kraft, 2018), a positive influence through ambidextrous leadership on performance for large companies (Cao, Q et. al., 2009, as cited in Kraft, 2018), and a positive influence through ambidextrous leadership on profits for SMEs (Chang, Y. Y., & Hughes, M., 2012, as cited in Kraft, 2018).

The combination of exploratory and exploitative behaviors that are ambidextrous can be successful even for large companies with extensive resource bases. Given the evidence of ambidextrous behavior from both theoretical and practical perspectives, some research has been dedicated to identifying the enabling factors for such action profiles (Cao, Q et. al., 2009, as cited in Kraft, 2018). In the positive relationship between the level of ambidexterity and effectiveness within organizations, it has been found that this relationship is supported by a flexible hierarchy on one side and clear process chains on the other. The interaction between exploratory and exploitative orientations has also been shown to be conducive to increasing company sales (Jansen et al, 2009, as cited in Kraft, 2018). In empirical studies, it was found that the levels of exploration and exploitation in business units are positively related to performance (Bucic et. al., 2010, as cited in Kraft, 2018).

Conclusion

In conclusion, to enhance employee performance in a company, including in the manufacturing sector, it is crucial for organizations to develop ambidextrous leadership. Ambidextrous leadership plays a significant role in improving employee performance. The conceptual framework shows that ambidextrous leadership affects the employee performance improvement. The achievement of employee performance should be supported by exploratory and exploitative behaviors. Exploratory behavior involves uncovering hidden potential in employees through in-depth examination and research, while exploitative behavior is the utilization of employee performance empowerment based on known potential through the exploration process. This model highlights the contribution of ambidextrous leadership to enhancing employee performance in manufacturing companies. Companies should not overlook ambidextrous leadership, which exhibits temporal flexibility—the ability to switch between exploratory and exploitative behaviors as needed in different situations.

This research provides recommendations for making ambidextrous leadership a top priority in businesses, including those in the manufacturing sector, especially in the face of business uncertainty in the VUCA era (Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, and

Ambiguity). The development and renewal of employee competencies must align with business demands, as employees are long-term assets that prepare opportunities for future business. Ambidextrous leaders are becoming a new trend in leadership styles that all companies must cultivate. The ability of leaders to simultaneously apply opposing approaches, focusing on innovation exploration and efficiency exploitation, is highly needed in today's business conditions.

In conclusion, ambidextrous leadership is essential for improving employee performance, particularly in the manufacturing sector. Companies in the manufacturing sector critically require ambidextrous leadership as a primary prerequisite to confront business uncertainty in the VUCA era. It is imperative for companies to cultivate ambidextrous leadership styles among their leaders to encourage employees to engage in innovation, respond intelligently, and smoothly facilitate innovation implementation, ultimately achieving productivity targets. Companies should allocate a dedicated budget for investing in education and training programs aimed at developing leaders with ambidextrous leadership styles. The investment in education and training to groom leaders with ambidextrous leadership styles is essential, as it directly correlates with achieving maximum employee performance. Ambidexterity in leadership can provide companies with advantages by enhancing both internal processes' efficiency and innovation capabilities. This literature review demonstrates that while there is an extensive body of research on the positive impact of ambidextrous leadership, several challenges remain, such as budget availability, commitment from top management, and corporate cultural differences. Future research on different leadership styles can make significant contributions to both the scientific knowledge and practical applications in the context of sustainable leadership and business management.

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